

ISic3078

I.Sicily inscription 3078

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.11.10 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-12-21 - Jonathan Prag minor edits

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Found 1954 in a sarcophagus in grotta di Fragapane, rotonda n.XII

Coordinates

37.290161, 13.589661

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. · χαί·ροις · πα·ρο·δ[εῖτα]
2. πα·ρὰ · Φα·βίου · Σα
3. τορ·νί·λου · ζή·σαν
4. τος · ἔτη · κ·ά' · μῆ·νας
5. · ἡ' · ἡμέρας · ι·ε' · ἀ·έ·ρι · μὴ φόβι

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645430

EDR 136074

EDCS 64900839

PHI 331797

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